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Passive Precision Farming reshapes the Agricultural Sector

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Increasing challenges in food provision along with the need for environmental protection require a rethinking in the agricultural sector. Digitalization and automation approaches, such as precision farming, provide a promising approach to optimize resource usage and efficiency. The provision of passive digital services for monitoring and managing small scale farms has the potential to reshape the sector, as it supports existing infrastructures and ecosystems near the consumer rather than introducing large scale automated agricultural systems which are more volatile to supply chain disruptions.

Sustainable food production exploiting embedded computing systems

In the next 40 years, the demand for food is expected to increase by approximately 70% worldwide. Population growth, in combination with more frequent and intense climate extreme conditions, will push conventional farming towards more efficient and sustainable farming solutions [1]. This creates the need for alternative and innovative agricultural solutions in order to decrease the use of pesticides, to keep food supply sustainable, to maximize yields and, in parallel, to minimize negative effects on the environment. Precision farming [2] is a highly promising technology to achieve these goals, i.e., food safety, security and environmental protection. For example, IoT technologies and corresponding data analytics are used in pest management or towards minimizing the use of antibiotics. Large agricultural organizations already benefit from digitalization and industrialization. They do have the capacities and space to deploy and maintain large networks (e.g., LoRaWAN infrastructures, etc.), machines for automated caring of the crops and resources for operating them. Like any monoculture, which is typical for large scale fields, they have increased need for maintenance and are dependent on a complex supply chain.

Traditional small farms, on the other hand, do not have the means for large-scale digitalization and automation. Farmers often have many years – even generations – of experience working on their land in a sustainable way and are close to the consumer. Their land, in most cases, is scattered and distributed over a larger territory with non-homogeneous shapes and

characteristics. This, by its very nature, prevents large scale monocultures. Small scale farms represent a significant proportion of the agricultural sector (representative numbers from 2021 from Germany [3] indicate that nearly 25% of all German farms are below 10 hectares where only about 1% of all German farms are larger than 500 hectares). Climate change also contributes to more dynamic conditions at small scale, scattered and uneven farmland, resulting in non-homogeneous microclimate distributions, as shown in Figure 1 by using the LAYERS approach (<https://layers.hemav.com>). In the figure, different conditions, referred to as “microclimate zones”, are indicated with different colours. This condition differences indicate potential to improve sustainability and yield through localized treatment.

Figure 1: Multi-spectral image analysis of a representative vineyard showing microclimate zones

Thus, small-scale farms can benefit from monitoring their conditions through employment of embedded and cyber physical systems in customized settings. The collected data are used for expert advice and, typically, for remote support. Small-scale farm diversity and fragmentation emphasizes the needs for easy, efficient, and finely granular information collection and availability. As microclimate or plant growing conditions change, farmers adjust their actions and interventions manually, based on their experience; for example, they may intervene adapting local irrigation intensity. Currently, achieving similar interventions with highly automated systems is significantly more expensive than merely monitoring with sensors, due to land fragmentation. In these environments, semi-automated, rather than fully automated, interventions are the norm; this approach is referred to as *passive precision farming*. Passive precision farming for small-scale farms is pivotal in terms of profitability, sustainability, and food safety.

Passive precision farming employing drones

A representative example of passive precision farming is the pilot case of a small-scale vineyard

in Burgenland, Austria, which collects microclimate zone data by a drone operator¹. Data are gathered for evaluation of suboptimal microclimate conditions including water, stress and early-stage indication of plant health conditions; sensor data include temperature, wind speed, air-, leaf-, and soil-humidity, sun intensity, etc., which may result in plant diseases, such as powdery-mildew [4].

The specific vineyard lacks broadband infrastructure to collect data because of several factors, such as geographical distance from urban broadband network nodes and missing lines of sight due to hilly terrain. Setting up a dedicated infrastructure, such as LoRaWAN or WLAN, is expensive and requires significant power for network interfaces and connections [5]. Such a dedicated and permanent sensor infrastructure would also result in frequent changes of sensor batteries and increased maintenance cost. Thus, it is desirable to have a service where information collected by landbound sensors is delivered to a mobile gateway, such as a drone. Drone service providers already offer services like the geographic recording of the terrain for farmers. The sporadic, non-permanent and continuous collection of sensor data via a drone-based system is an attractive option / add-on for information collection as a service; for example, a drone can collect the data measurements of land-bound sensors during a flight over a field, relieving farmers from installing semi-permanent sensors themselves and enabling them to outsource the activity to a service provider. Semi-permanent sensor deployment allows the service operator to flexibly collect information from defined locations in a vineyard for the given service period.

Dynamic information collection via drones

A typical implementation of the service is shown in Figure 2, where a monitoring system is built exploiting an existing drone service that collects multispectral data. The drone is equipped with a Data Collection Unit (DCU) that implements a software WLAN access point. When the drone approaches the deployed land-bound sensors (or the computing unit on which each sensor is mounted), sensors connect to the DCU, and the sensor-collected data are transferred. This applies to data collected since the previous connection to the DCU, i.e., the previous time the drone passed by. When the drone completes its mission, it returns to the service provider (operator) who executes another DCU for harvesting all data, it connects to this aggregating DCU and transmits all collected data to it.

Cybersecurity is an integral part of the overall service and its system components, because it specifies its trustworthiness. Cyberattacks on the service can lead to financial damages due to loss of harvest or reduction of harvest quality. The attack surface is wide at all levels, ranging from

¹ This pilot case was part of the Comp4Drones project, which is an ECSEL Joint Under-taking (JU) under grant agreement No 826610.

sensors and networks to drones. Potential attackers include individual or groups of competitors, hobbyists and others. In general, threats to data acquisition technologies and to unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) constitute one of the most pressing security challenges in smart agriculture [7].

In the described service, as shown in Figure 2, cybersecurity is achieved employing hardware security modules and detecting data anomalies at the DCU of the drone during data collection. Derivation from expected behaviour, such as unrealistic increase of temperature between reading times or station locations, constitutes an anomaly. An anomaly will trigger the removal and disconnection of potentially compromised or faulty sensors from the system.

Figure 2: Passive precision farming as a service for a vineyard in Austria

Evaluation in the field

This service has been developed and evaluated in the field. The security framework has been implemented exploiting the Eclipse Arrowhead Framework [6], while threat modelling has been

performed through the ThreatGet tool (www.threatget.com) which enables threat modelling for CPS and IoT systems. As Figure 2 outlines, the complete service is composed of seven steps: (1) vineyard data are collected by sensor nodes, (2) a secure connection is established between drone and node, (3) collected sensor data are transferred, (4) analysis is conducted for anomaly (fraud/manipulation) detection, (5) a secure connection is established to the aggregator's DCU, (6) and data are transferred to this aggregator's DCU, (7) all collected data are transferred to a server for data analysis.

For the evaluation of the service in the vineyard, positions for land-bound sensors have been identified through an analysis of multispectral images and a digital terrain model that takes into account the water stress level and Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) evaluations; NDVI is a metric which indicates the health of the plants, based on near-infrared light reflected back into the atmosphere.

These parameters cover a large set of the required information to investigate, such as the susceptibility of grapevines to infection by the powdery mildew [4]. During the data collection flight for multispectral data, the drone flies along a predefined path over the sensors; after validation of a secure communication, the drone flies towards the next point on its preconfigured route in the vineyard. After completing data collection, the drone lands at its home position and transfers the data to a base station, where data are aggregated, processed, and submitted to the vineyard owner. Figure 3 shows the DCU-mounted drone, where the DCU is the yellow box implemented using a RaspberryPi (a), and the sensor nodes as they are cased in a weather-proof chassis (b).

Figure 3. Evaluation of passive precision farming

Conclusions

Emerging embedded and cyber-physical systems enable new business models and services to support existing agricultural environments, ensuring food safety and security in an increasingly challenging future due to climate change and resource scarcities. Services to the agricultural sector can be effective and efficient, applying similar ideas as in the IT industry exploiting cloud technologies and the “everything-as-a-service” concept. Clearly, large and small farms require different approaches to technological support for farming. Large scale farms can employ industrialization approaches, while small farms need to address geographic sparsity with heterogeneous conditions and multiple plants. In small farms, monitoring and obtaining detailed data is useful, and often critical, but developing and training a fully automated expert system is costly. Passive precision farming provides a cost-effective approach that enables effective decision making by small farmers who are limited in resources and leads to efficient farming and safe agricultural products. It clearly contributes to the preservation and competitiveness of traditional, established and sustainable agriculture infrastructures.

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